

Photoreduction of Diazoketones with Isopropanol in Visible Light

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The photoreductions of α -diazacetophenone^{1,2} and α -diaz-*p*-methoxyacetophenone³ in ultraviolet light were reported. The photoreduction of α -diazacetophenones with isopropanol in the presence of visible light was studied previously on a qualitative basis⁴.

The photoreduction of α -diazacetophenone and substituted α -diazacetophenones with isopropanol in presence of visible light has been studied quantitatively by glc estimation and is reported in this communication.

Cowan *et al.*¹ studied the photolysis of diazoketones in cyclohexene and from the same product distribution in both direct and sensitised photolysis concluded that there was intersystem crossing of the singlet diazoketones to the triplet state. The triplet diazoketones decomposed into triplet ketocarbenes which then further reacted. Padwa and Layton² studied the direct and sensitised photolysis of α -diazacetophenone in methanol, ethanol and isopropanol in uv light. In both direct and sensitised photolysis, triplet ketocarbene is produced. As singlet ketocarbene is the precursor of Wolff rearrangement, this explains the formation of isopropyl phenylacetate in negligible amount from sensitised photolysis of α -diazacetophenone in isopropanol. The triplet ketocarbene abstracts hydrogen from isopropanol to form acetophenone. The abstraction of hydrogen by triplet ketocarbene from methanol or ethanol is endoenergetic and consequently intersystem crossing of the triplet state to the singlet state may now compete with abstraction of hydrogen. So methyl or ethyl phenylacetate is obtained in better yield when the photolysis in uv light is carried out in methanol or ethanol. Moore and Ketchum⁵ observed that in the photoreduction-dimerisation of benzophenone, the presence of naphthalene in very low concentration sharply

reduced the yield of the product and concluded that naphthalene deactivated the triplet state of benzophenone.

Results and Discussion

In the photoreduction of diazoketones with isopropanol in visible light, it has been found that only the reduced product is formed. No rearranged product is obtained. The products are obtained in fairly good yields and in pure condition. In glc of the photoreduced products of α -diazacetophenone, no peak corresponding to 1,2-dibenzoyl ethane or α -isopropoxyacetophenone was obtained. No products other than acetophenone or substituted acetophenones were obtained in column chromatography of the reduced products. From the yields of the reduced products, it appears that the substituents in the benzene ring of the diazoketones do not have any significant effect on the photoreduction of diazoketones. The yield of the reduced product from α -diaz-*p*-nitroacetophenone was much less compared to those of the other three diazoketones. This may be due to the fact that α -diaz-*p*-nitroacetophenone is less stable than the other three diazoketones. There was some polymeric decomposition of diazoketones during photoreduction.

When the photolysis of the diazoketones was carried out in methanol or benzene in visible light, the diazoketones did not react. There was very little decomposition of the diazoketones. After the photolysis, the diazoketones were recovered almost quantitatively. This shows that unlike photoreduction^{1,2} in uv light, the diazoketones do not decompose in visible light. The undecomposed diazoketones are, therefore, reduced by isopropanol in visible light. It has also been found that in the photoreduction of diazoketones with isopropanol in visible light, naphthalene in very low

concentration in the reaction mixture has sharply reduced the yields of the products. Naphthacene deactivates the triplet state of diazoketones. It is, therefore, concluded that undecomposed diazoketones are reduced in the triplet state by isopropanol in visible light.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Glc was carried out on a Hewlett-Packard 5730 A instrument with a stainless steel column (16 cm × 0.32 cm) packed with 10% u.c.w. 982 on 100-120 mesh Gas chrom Q, nitrogen being used as the carrier gas. Acetophenone, *p*-methoxyacetophenone and *p*-chloroacetophenone were identified by comparison of glc retention times (1.09, 1.66 and 2.76 min respectively, isothermal 110°). *p*-Nitroacetophenone was identified by comparison of glc retention time (1.37, isothermal 150°).

TABLE 1-PHOTOLYSIS OF DIAZOKETONES WITH ISOPROPANOL IN VISIBLE LIGHT

SL. no.	Diazoketone	Molarity of naphthacene × 10 ⁻⁴	Recovered diazoketone ^a g	Yield of reduced product ^b %	W ₂ /W ₁ ^c
1.	<i>α</i> -Diazoacetophenone (1.0 g)	Nil	0.20	68.1	-
		2.34	0.37	49.8	0.73
		4.68	0.45	38.8	0.58
		9.36	0.56	30.3	0.45
2.	<i>α</i> -Diazo- <i>p</i> -methoxyacetophenone (1.0 g)	Nil	0.23	69.2	-
		2.34	0.36	44.6	0.64
		4.68	0.49	28.1	0.41
		9.36	0.52	15.3	0.22
3.	<i>p</i> -Chloro- <i>α</i> -diazoacetophenone (1.0 g)	Nil	0.20	61.9	-
		2.34	0.28	43.2	0.70
		4.68	0.34	25.7	0.41
		9.36	0.40	12.9	0.21
4.	<i>α</i> -Diazo- <i>p</i> -nitroacetophenone (1.0 g)	Nil	0.18	53.2	-
		2.34	0.26	39.3	0.74
		4.68	0.30	30.1	0.57
		9.36	0.31	19.6	0.37

^aRecovered from column chromatography.

^bObtained by glc estimation.

^cYield of reduced product : W₁ = in absence of naphthacene, W₂ = in presence of naphthacene.

Photoreduction of diazoketones with isopropanol in visible light : α -Diazoacetophenone (1.0 g; m.p. 46–47°) in isopropanol (200 ml) was photolysed (200 Watt visible Philips lamp, 20 h) under N₂. Isopropanol was then removed and the residue (0.85 g) was found to contain acetophenone (0.56 g) by glc estimation. On chromatography over activated alumina, acetophenone (0.48 g) and unreacted α -diazacetophenone (0.20 g) were separated.

Similar experiments were done with α -diazo-*p*-methoxyacetophenone, *p*-chloro- α -diazacetophenone and α -diazo-*p*-nitroacetophenone (Table 1). The same procedure was followed using naphthacene in different concentrations in the reaction mixtures.

Photolysis of diazoketones in methanol in visible light : α -Diazoacetophenone (1.0 g) was photolysed in methanol (200 ml) under identical conditions as described above. No acetophenone was detected by glc. On chromatography over alumina, unreacted α -diazacetophenone (0.83 g) was separated. Similar results were obtained from the photolysis of α -diazo-*p*-methoxyacetophenone, *p*-chloro- α -diazacetophenone and α -diazo-*p*-nitroacetophenone in methanol in visible light.

Photolysis of diazoketones in benzene in visible light : α -Diazoacetophenone (1.0 g) was photolysed in benzene (200 ml) under identical conditions as in the previous experiments. No acetophenone was detected by glc. On chromatographic separation over alumina, unreacted α -diazacetophenone (0.72 g) was obtained. Similar results were obtained from the photolysis of the substituted diazoketones in benzene in visible light.

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